

Histopathological Study of Skin Adnexal Tumors with Special Insight into Rare Variants: A Retrospective Study of 48 Cases in a Tertiary Care Hospital

Mahata M¹, Paul M², Chakraborty B³, Pradhan R⁴, Mondal S⁵

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, College of Medicine and Sagore Dutta Hospital

²Demonstrator, Department of Pathology, College of Medicine & Sagore Dutta Hospital

³Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, College of Medicine & Sagore Dutta Hospital

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, College of Medicine & Sagore Dutta Hospital

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Rampurhat Government Medical College & Hospital

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Rajashree Pradhan

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Abstract:

Background: Skin adnexal tumors (SATs) are uncommon lesions and include diverse group of tumors, both benign and malignant. Benign tumors are more common compared to the malignant ones. Although the malignant tumors are rare, they are locally aggressive, have high propensity to distant metastasis and are associated with poorer prognosis. The diagnosis is established essentially by histopathological examination which is still considered as the gold standard technique.

Aims and Objectives: Skin adnexal tumors (SATs) are rare neoplasms infrequently encountered in the routine surgical pathology practice. This study aimed to find the clinical presentation and the histopathological features of SATs along with differentiating benign from malignant tumors.

Materials and Methods: This was retrospective study done in a tertiary care hospital over a period of two years (June 2022 to May 2024). All the SATs reported during this period were analyzed for their clinical features, age, sex incidence and their gross and histopathological features.

Results: The total number of cases diagnosed as SATs were 48 which included pigmented eccrine poroma, eccrine spiradenoma, syringocystadenoma papilliferum, nodular hidradenoma, proliferating trichilemmal cyst, trichoepithelioma, pilomatrixoma, Trichoblastoma and epidermal cysts.

Conclusion: SATs are uncommon entities most of which are benign. Malignant neoplasms are extremely rare and have a very poor prognosis including reduced survival and high rate of distant metastasis. This study emphasizes on proper categorization of skin adnexal tumors which helps in optimal patient management and better patient outcome.

Keywords: Skin Adnexal Tumors, Histopathology, Gold Standard.

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Introduction

SATs are unique group of tumors which include large and varied categories of neoplasms with differentiation towards pilosebaceous apparatus, apocrine and eccrine sweat glands. Their origin from pluripotent stem cells within the epidermis or its appendageal structures may be the reason for such varied characteristics [1].

Even though most SATs are benign, diagnosing them may have important implications. They might be markers for syndromes associated with internal malignancies, such as trichilemmomas in Cowden's disease and sebaceous adenomas in Muir-Torre syndrome [2]. Diagnosis of SATs is quite challenging, both in their classification and histogenesis, mainly because of their overlapping

morphological features and their heterogeneous patterns of differentiation. The diagnosis of SATs is based mainly on histopathology, which is considered gold standard, with the limited role of immunohistochemistry [3]. There are very few clinicopathological studies, on skin adnexal tumors, available in the literature [4].

This study aims at evaluating the histopathological features of skin adnexal tumors, in a tertiary care hospital, in last two years, with special insight into rare variants, along with correlation with clinical profile of the patients. This will certainly aid in proper diagnosis of skin adnexal tumors which in turn will help in optimal patient management and improving the morbidity and mortality.

Aims & Objectives

Histopathological evaluation of skin adnexal tumors with special emphasis on its rare variants

Materials and Methods

Study design, Duration and Place of study: This was a retrospective study conducted over a period of 2yrs from June 2022 to May 2024 in a tertiary care hospital,

Inclusion Criteria: All the cases of nodular skin lesions undergoing lesional biopsy or wide local excision (as applicable) sent to the Pathology department were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: All the cases with pathologies other than skin adnexal tumors were excluded from the study.

Relevant Clinical Data: All the relevant clinical data such as age of the patient, gender of the patient, site of the skin lesion and appearance of the skin lesions were collected from the clinical records.

Specimen Handling: After receiving the skin biopsy samples in our department of pathology, fixation followed by grossing of the specimen were done. Tissue processing was done and hematoxylin and Eosin-stained slides were prepared for routine microscopic examination.

Histopathological Parameters: All the cases of skin biopsy samples were re-evaluated by two independent histopathologists and final diagnosis was made.

Ethical Clearance: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics committee (IEC).

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was done using software version 20.0. Results were expressed in number & percentage.

Result

In our study, a total of 62 skin lesions were studied out of which 14 cases (22.58%) were non-neoplastic skin lesions and 48 cases (77.41%) were skin adnexal tumors (SAT). (Table 1)

The most common age group presenting with skin adnexal tumors was 41-60 years (28,58.33%). Skin adnexal tumors were predominantly seen in males (28,58.33%).

The most common site of presentation of skin adnexal tumors were in the scalp (33,68.75%) followed by upper extremity (09,18.75%). 45 out of 48 (93.75%) skin adnexal tumors presented as solitary skin lesions, rest (3/48,6.25%) were multiple skin lesions. (Table 2)

Out of 48 Skin adnexal tumors that were evaluated, Trichilemmal cyst was found in 12 cases (25%), Pilomatrixoma was found in 9 cases (18.75%), Nodular hidradenoma was found in 8 cases (16.6%), Eccrine poroma was found in 7 cases (14.58%), Trichoepithelioma was found in 3 cases (6.2%), Proliferating trichilemmal cyst and Trichoblastoma were found in 2 cases (4.1%) each and Hidradenoma papilliferum, Eccrine spiradenoma and syringocystadenoma papilliferum were found in 1 case (2.08%) each. (Table 3)

Table 1: Number of Skin Adnexal Tumors studied

Total number of skin lesional biopsy/ wide excision	Non-neoplastic Lesions	Skin Adnexal Tumors (SAT)
62	14 -Epidermal cyst (8,16.6%) -Seborrheic keratosis (6,12.5%)	48

Table 2: Clinical presentation of Skin Adnexal Tumors (n=48)

Serial number	Clinical parameters	Number	Percentage
1	AGE (years)		
	-20-40	12	25%
	-41-60	28	58.33%
	->60	08	16.66%
2	SEX		
	-Male	28	58.33%
	-Female	20	41.66%
3	SITE		
	-Scalp	33	68.75%
	-Upper extremity	09	18.75%
	-Lower extremity	04	8.3%
	-Trunk	02	4.1%
4	APPEARANCE		
	-Solitary	45	93.75%
	-Multiple	03	6.25%

Table 3: Histopathological categories of Skin Adnexal Tumors (n=48)

Serial number	Histopathological Categories	Number	Percentage
1	Trichilemmal cyst	12	25%
2	Pilomatrixoma	09	18.75%
3	Proliferating trichilemmal cyst	02	4.1%
4	Nodular Hidradenoma	08	16.6%
5	Trichoblastoma	02	4.1%
6	Eccrine Poroma	07	14.58%
7	Hidradenoma Papilliferum	01	2.08%
8	Trichoepithelioma	03	6.2%
9	Eccrine Spiradenoma	01	2.08%
10	Syringocystadenoma Papilliferum	01	2.08%

Discussion

The diagnosis of skin adnexal tumors is always challenging due to varied presentation of the lesions. The complicated nomenclature along with huge number of tumors with variants increases the diagnostic dilemma.

The controlled proliferation of the hair follicles, sebaceous glands, apocrine glands and eccrine glands results in benign tumors of epidermal appendages. [4,5] The etiology of malignant adnexal carcinomas is mostly unknown; however, ultraviolet light and radiation have been implicated in their pathogenesis [6]. Most of them present with varied clinical presentation such as papules, plaques and nodules making the clinical diagnosis of the cases are often difficult [4,7-10]. Total number of skin biopsies evaluated in our study was 62, out of which 14 were non-neoplastic lesions. The non-neoplastic lesions were 8 cases of epidermal cyst (16.6%) and 6 cases seborrheic keratosis (12.5%).

Majority of patients in our study were in the age group 41 to 60 years (58.33%). This result was higher to that reported by Gayathri et al that showed the average age was 35.2 years and Samaila et al. with an average age with 33 years old. [11, 12] In the study by Nair et al. also commonest age group of presentation was 11-20 years [13]

The number of cases occurring in males was 28 (58.33%) and in females 20 cases (41.66%). Analysis of the sex ratio (M: F=1.4:1) revealed male predominance, which was consistent with the literature [4,14,15].

In our study, most of the skin adnexal tumors were located in the head and neck region, precisely in the scalp (33 cases) which accounts for 68.75% cases. This was mainly due to great abundance of cutaneous adnexal structures at these sites [16]. The limbs and the trunk were less affected, upper extremity 9 cases (18.75%), lower extremity 4 cases (8.3%) and trunk 2 cases (4.1%). This is in accordance with the study of Nair et al [13] In our study, trichilemmal cyst was the predominant

histological type accounting for 25% of the cases (12 cases) followed by pilomatrixoma (9 cases; 18.75%), nodular hidradenoma (8 cases; 16.6%) and eccrine poroma (7 cases; 14.58%). According to the study by Radhika et al. most common benign tumor was nodular hidradenoma followed by sebaceous naevus [4]. In the study by Sharma et al., most common tumors were clear cell hidradenoma and pilomatrixoma followed by eccrine poroma [17].

The important and relevant histopathological findings of some of the interesting cases of our study are discussed herewith. Nodular cystic hidradenoma accounts for 16.6% cases in our study. Histopathologically the tumor is composed of solid and cystic areas. The solid area consists of two types of cells: eosinophilic or polygonal cells and clear cells (Figure 1). The cystic spaces are filled with eosinophilic hyaline material [18].

In our study, eccrine poroma accounts for 14.58% cases, this includes a single case of pigmented eccrine poroma also. Histopathological examination reveals a well circumscribed lesion, with uniform monomorphic cuboidal tumor cells, lying in broad anastomosing bands. Small duct lumina are also evident in some areas. Some lesion also contains variable amount of melanin granules or pigment (Figure 2). No features of atypia are seen in any of the cases [19].

Trichoblastoma is a greater histopathological mimicker of basal cell carcinoma. It accounts for 4.1% cases in our study. This tumor usually appears as a dermal lesion without any epidermal connection. It consists of variable sized lobules of primitive basaloid cells with characteristic peripheral palisading and intervening fibrous stroma [20]. Eccrine spiradenoma, accounting for 2.08% of the cases in our study, is another important skin adnexal tumor. On histopathological examination this tumor appears as sharply demarcated basophilic lobules of tumor cells in dermis. The tumor comprises of two types of tumor cells: small, dark basaloid cells with hyperchromatic nuclei and large pale cell with ovoid nuclei. The large, pale cell tend to be toward

the center of the lesion (Figure 3). Duct-like structures and sometimes cysts with eosinophilic material in lumen are also evident in focal areas [21].

Figure 4 shows characteristic microscopic features of proliferating trichilemmal cyst.

Figure 1: Showing features of Nodular cystic hidradenoma (H&E,100x) [inset shows H&E,400x]

Figure 2: Showing features of Pigmented eccrine poroma (H&E,100x) [inset shows H&E,400x]

Figure 3: Showing features of Eccrine spiradenoma (H&E,100x) [inset shows H&E,400x]

Figure 4: Showing features of Proliferating trichilemmal cyst (H&E,100x) [inset shows H&E,400x]

Conclusion

We concluded that due to varied clinical presentation skin adnexal tumors (SATs) pose a great difficulty in the diagnosis. Histopathology is considered as the gold standard and is integral part of the diagnostic workup. Detailed knowledge of SATs helps us to solve the diagnostic dilemma and ambiguity related to various lineage of such tumors. The varied presentation of these tumors like ulceration or pigmentation may also lead to confusion with other epithelial and soft tissue tumors. Therefore, accurate histopathological diagnosis plays pivotal role in the patient management.

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